

Can “Sport Brand” Products be Sponsored? In Customer Communication, Perception of Image and Purchasing Decision

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Abstract – A research framework on customer communication and image perception is summarized through a review of relevant literature. Can sports sponsorship influence fans' attitudes and purchase decisions about sponsors' products, and understanding the link between sports sponsorship and purchase decisions can help companies achieve their sustainability philosophy through sports. Through the literature, it is shown that sports sponsorship has the potential to be an effective tool to facilitate customer communication and improve brand image perceptions, ultimately leading to increased sales. This study could add some new thinking to the way sports brands are marketed in order to increase their awareness and marketability.

Keywords: Sports sponsorship, Customer communication, Perception of image, Purchasing decision

Introduction

Today, sponsorship is an important part of sporting events (Melovic et al., 2019). Corporate involvement in sports sponsorship arrangements increases both brand exposure and the opportunity for companies to gain access to sell their products among sports fans. Bringing previously distant stakeholders closer together (Cunningham, Cornwell, & Coote, 2009).

Sponsorship activities in sports are an important area of research in the marketing literature. Sponsorship can be defined as "an investment in an activity, in cash or in kind, in exchange for the right to use the activity. Sponsorship can be defined as "an investment in an activity in cash or in kind in exchange for access to exploitable business potential associated with that activity Sponsorship can be defined as "an investment in an activity in cash or in kind in exchange for access to exploitable business potential associated with that activity (Meenaghan, 1991, p. 36). According to this according to this definition, researchers generally agree that sponsorship can be seen as a business-to-business relationship. mutually beneficial relationship between the sponsor and the sport entity (Farrelly, Quester, & Greyser, 2005; Henseler et al, 2011). This perspective implies that the sport entity earns monetary support or other in-kind resources to improve the quality of the team and the standard of management of the club, while the sponsor receives tangible and intangible benefits associated with the sport entity (Chen & Zhang, 2011; Yang, Sparks, & Lee, 2008). For example, benefits may be associated with benefits with overcoming cultural barriers (Cousens, Babiak, & Bradish, 2006), building relationships with media companies (Chadwick & Thwaites, 2004), increasing brand awareness and promoting a positive brand image, reaching new target markets, and promoting sales and market share. By increasing loyalty, fending off competitors and gaining more opportunities for growth (Apostolopoulou & Papadimitriou, 2004). Even improve employee morale or promote employee recruitment (Barros & Silvestre, 2006).

Past research has shown that fans are emotionally invested when attending sporting events (Biscaia, Correia, Rosado, Biscaia, Correia, Rosado, Maroco, & Ross, 2012; Kwak, Kim, & Hirt, 2011; Madrigal, 2003), while global brands use this emotional impact of sports Global brands use this emotional impact of sports to connect with consumers (Santomier, 2008). In addition, Meenaghan (2001) argues that sponsor investment in professional sports teams creates an affinity effect among fans, which in turn influences their attitudes and behaviors toward their sponsors. Likewise, Parker and Fink (2010) argue that once the relationship between the team and the sponsor is established, the sponsor becomes part of a tight-knit network of fans. To this extent in this sense, understanding the role of team loyalty is critical to fans' evaluation of corporate sponsors is critical to fans' evaluation of corporate sponsors (Hong, 2011).

In essence, sports sponsorship has become a powerful marketing strategy. Companies use it to communicate with a wide range of external and internal audiences Companies use sports sponsorship to communicate with a wide range of external and internal audiences to differentiate themselves from their competitors (Cornwell, 2008), with the ultimate goal of directing consumer preferences toward the sponsor's product (Barros & Silvestre, 2006).

Literature Review

Sports sponsorship

Sponsorship is not only an important communication tool in the contemporary marketing mix, but also an important source of revenue for sports organizations (Independent Sports Group, 2009). Most definitions of sponsorship emphasize the exchange of resources between two parties that can produce mutual benefits (Walliser, 2003). For example, McCarville and Copeland (McCarville & Copeland, 1994) describe sponsorship as a relationship in which a sponsor exchanges resources (e.g., cash, products, or labor) with an individual, product, or workforce with a person, cause, or event (the sponsored party, or property of the sport sponsorship), and the sponsor expects this exchange to produce an investment return. While the event or cause being sponsored (Speed & Thompson, 2000), may involve some charitable intent, the sponsor also seeks to help strategically, i.e., to advertise the brand. Examples include peripheral signage of sports venues and organizational logos peripheral signage of sports venues and organizational logos on athletes' apparel (Abratt & Grobler, 1989).

Many studies have investigated the motivation of corporate involvement in sponsorship. In earlier investigations (Quinn, 1982), corporate involvement in sponsorship was primarily an ad hoc response to organizational and individual requests, with the development of a corporate image as a secondary motivation. Current motivations reflect a growing recognition of sponsorship as a means of achieving profit-oriented business goals, including increased market penetration, brand image perception, media exposure, and subsequent contribution to sales. (Arthur, 1999; Javalgi, Traylor, Gross, & Lampman, 1994; Stotlar, 1999; Walliser, 2003).

Sponsorship spending on sports, events, and the arts has grown steadily in recent years (IEG, 2012). According to the International Events Group (IEG, 2012) the global sponsorship market was estimated at \$48.6 billion in 2011, with approximately 68% of that money invested in the sports industry. During this period, sports sponsorship in North America totaled \$12.4 billion (IEG, 2012), while sponsorship in the European soccer market while the European soccer market was estimated at \$20.9 billion for the 2010-2011 season (Deloitte, 2012). The growth situation shows that sports sponsorship is an important marketing tool for companies and can be an important source of revenue for corporate sponsors.

Sponsorship at sporting events is an exceptional way for companies to establish deeper ties and integration with sports organizations, and also to introduce their brands and products through advertising. In most local or international sporting events, sponsors have an important role and position (Melovic et al., 2019). Today, we rarely see a sports story without sponsorship and we rarely see a sports event without sponsorship.

Customer communication

Sports sponsorship offers a variety of benefits, while it is also a more powerful form of marketing to communicate with customers. Generally, sponsorship occupies a unique position in the marketing mix because it effectively builds brand awareness, provides different marketing platforms and valuable communication and hospitality opportunities (Melovic et al., 2019). Over the past few decades, corporate sports sponsorship has

grown in popularity globally. Sports sponsorship has transformed from a corporate giving concept to a primary marketing strategy used by corporations, becoming a key element of the marketing strategy used by large companies to create brand value and gain a competitive advantage (Henseler, Wilson, & Westberg, 2011).

Sponsorship marketing efforts can be influenced by popular culture. This is especially true when considering global sponsorship in sports, meaning sporting events with different popular cultures in different countries. In this case, sponsorship effectiveness may be influenced by pop culture factors (Melovic et al., 2019). Sports sponsorship serves as an important marketing tool for corporate sponsors and a valuable source of revenue for professional sports teams (Bühler, Hefferman, & Hewson, 2007). Irwin and Asimakopoulos (1992) argue that sponsors prefer to invest in sports teams that have strong ties with their fans. Fans will have a favorable opinion of teams with which they interact and communicate better and will transfer this favorable opinion to sports sponsors, which will increase the liking of sports sponsors' brands and products (Madrigal, 2001). Recent empirical research has explored the role of fans' psychological attachment to teams. Fans' psychological attachment to the team leads to positive responses to sponsors such as sponsorship awareness (Ko, Kim, Claussen, & Kim, 2008; Lee, Harris, & Lyberger, 2011), attitudes toward sponsors, and purchase intentions (Gwinner & Bennett, 2008; Hong, 2011).

The same is true for partnerships with other celebrity athletes in terms of, for example, brand image endorsements. The constant demand for sports athletes to be able to perform and interact with their fans, driven by sponsors and the media, has led to the creation of a strong social image for the athletes in society. Corporate sponsors pay high amounts of money to associate their brand image with the social image of the athletes and use their strong fan base for the purpose of communicating with their customers (Knittel et al., 2013). When selecting a sports athlete, sponsors generally consider two things, whether the celebrity has a positive social image as perceived by the target market; and whether they are trustworthy, thus giving the brand credibility. For example, Le Bron James' lifetime contract with Nike worth over \$1 billion is an extreme example. Sponsors are willing to associate their brand image with the social image of the athlete's athletes. The sports industry says that it is financially beneficial for brands to associate with high-profile athletes by having athletes give motivational speeches, host sales meetings and add to the launch of new products. Launching events such as fun contests with sports fan customers and sports fan meet and greets can better promote new products and facilitate product development (Katz, 1994). Example. Stephen Curry's endorsement deal with Under Armour reportedly doubled the financial value of his brand (Keshkar et al., 2019) The accomplishments of certain star sports players can also be used to build pride in a company and contribute to the development of a corporate culture (Strasser & Becklund 1991).

Thus, by interacting and communicating with sports fan customers, sponsored brands can increase the level of response to the sponsored brand and can be associated with the image promoted by the brand, which may also generate considerable brand awareness and purchase intent (Ledwith, 1984).

Perception of Image

Consumer Relationship

The results of previous studies have shown that sports sponsorship has a direct positive impact on sports fans' perceptions and attitudes toward sponsors and their products (Hamel and Prahalad, 1994). We believe that association with an appropriate entity can increase the perceived customer value of a company's product or service the customer value of the company's product or service (Amis et al., 1997). Sports brand development, especially image enhancement, can be mutually beneficial by combining a sports organization with a prestigious brand (Howard & Crompton, 1995).

Intangible resources are company or brand image and reputation (Conner, 1991; Grant, 1991; Hall, 1992). Similarly, in order to increase the public perception of a brand or company, brand owners choose to enter into sponsorship agreements to change or enhance the image and reputation of the company or brand (Meenaghan, 1991; Mintel, 1994; Witcher et al., 1991). On the one hand, image and reputation are factors that enhance a brand's competitive advantage. On the other hand, sports sponsorship has been shown to be an effective tool for changing and enhancing a company's image and reputation. Therefore, we believe that sports sponsorship should be considered as an important resource that can help companies secure a competitive advantage position. In order for the resulting advantage to be sustainable, sponsorship, which is the basis of the

advantage, must be developed as a distinct competency area within the company. Prahalad and Hamel (1990) and Hamel and Prahalad (1994) argue that companies that have developed a sustainable competitive advantage have focused on being world leaders in a small number of "core competencies". They define core competencies as "the combination of skills and technologies that enable a firm to deliver specific benefits to its customers" (Hamel and Prahalad, 1994). For a few companies, such as McDonald's, Nike, Anheuser-Busch, and Coca-Cola, the time, effort, and money invested in sports sponsorship can make it a skill set that gives them the ability to strive for world leadership. In Hamel and Prahalad's view, for a sports sponsorship agreement to develop into a unique capability, it must have three components. First, the sponsorship can provide a significant increase in the perceived value of the product or service offered to the customer. Second, the uniqueness of the corporate sponsorship; in other words, the sponsorship asset must be uniquely owned in order to distinguish the company from its competitors. And more realistically for most companies, sponsorship is seen as one of many skills that, when bundled with other activities, can contribute to brand awareness, such as marketing and communications.

Health Awareness

A positive brand image brings a healthy and sunny sense of sports branding, but it should be acknowledged that there are inherent risks associated with any sponsorship. The person being sponsored is also a key stakeholder that benefits from the sponsorship. For example, sports organizations often rely on sponsorship to remain financially solvent and continue to support sports programs. In addition, obtaining sponsorship is a competitive process, "with sports programs competing in an ever-changing and more competitive landscape" (Independent Sports Panel, 2009), and sport organizations are under increasing pressure to select sponsors that are good for their image because they are required to be socially responsible in their decisions and actions. As a result, sport management practitioners are faced with the dilemma of whether to accept or not to accept sponsorship from organizations that seek to promote potentially harmful products. For example, in 2010, a club declined sponsorship from an American brothel. The league's governing body warned that this could send the wrong message about the treatment of women, as it conflicted with the league's family-friendly values (ABC Sports, 2010). Similarly, when entering into an agreement, sponsors should actively choose athletes, teams or events that are compatible with their product image in an attempt to attract the attention of their fan customers and thus achieve a higher perception of their brand image. Further research on athletes suggests that in order for sponsors to effectively maximize their relationships with sports athletes, they must carefully select celebrities with the right social image or a better fit with their brand image. For example, a failed drug test (Ben Johnson) or a poorly organized event (1996 Olympics) can be extremely damaging to a sponsor with whom the relationship is close (Keshkar et al., 2019).

Social Responsibility

Therefore, socially responsible companies can use sports sponsorship to raise awareness of existing social and environmental issues while increasing the value of their products in the minds of consumers, thus amounting to increased product sales in order to contribute to society with sponsors spending more money in a sustainable way (Skinner et al., 2010). It is also possible to educate the fans of sports teams about the importance of sustainability and social responsibility through socially beneficial sponsorship, giving them a better chance to become active members of society. They become active members of society and implement these concepts in their daily lives. They implement these concepts in their daily lives. Thus, they have the potential to become an important factor in the promotion and dissemination of sustainable development practices throughout society. Part of the research also confirms how the sponsorship decisions of sports organizations can have an impact on the governance of sports organizations by influencing the legal and regulatory system, including government policies and the organization's own code of conduct, and conversely, legislation and institutions (Hu et al., 2016).

Purchasing Decision

Sport-team Fans

Customer loyalty is mentioned in the literature as a favorable attitude and sustained purchase behavior towards a brand (Wilkie, 1994), which can be interpreted as a function of perceived product advantages, social bonds and their synergistic effects (Oliver, 1997). In sports, team loyalty represents a psychological connection

to the team that allows fans to maintain consistent and persistent positive behaviors and attitudes toward the team (Funk & Co. 290 Biscaia et al. James, 2001). Numerous scholars have argued that the construct of loyalty should include both attitudes and behaviors (Bauer et al, 2008; Bee & Havitz, 2010; Bodet & Bernache-Assollant, 2011; Kaynak et al, 2008). Behavioral loyalty refers to actual purchases of team support (Stevens & Rosenberger, 2012) and can include following the team through the media on a regular basis during a season or a game, as well as money spent on team merchandise (Bodet & Bernache-Assollant, 2011).

Team Loyalty

In addition, attitudinal loyalty includes one's commitment to the team and attitudinal preferences (Bauer et al., 2008; Kaynak et al., 2008). The most common measures of attitudinal loyalty in sponsorship research are fan involvement and team involvement (Alexandris, Douka, Bakaloumi, & Tsasousi, 2008; Chen & Zhang, 2011). Fan involvement refers to interest in a sporting activity and personal perceived importance of the sporting activity (Ko et al., 2008; Shank & Beasley, 1998), while team identification represents the fan's perception that the team is an extension of him or her (Theodorakis, Wann, & Weaver, 2012; Wann, Melnick, Russell, & Pease, 2001). The attitudinal behavior of brand purchasing behavior is usually associated with strong attitudes toward the team (Kaynak et al., 2008; Stevens & Rosenberger, 2012). However, the reason for attending a game may be that the person was given a ticket by chance (Bauer et al., 2008). Thus, true loyalty exists only when consumers regularly purchase the product and show strong loyalty (Caruana, 2002; Kaynak et al., 2008).

Sports sponsorship involves the allocation of resources with the aim of achieving certain organizational goals (Slack and Bentz, 1996). As such, it is often described as a strategic activity by the marketing literature (Carter, 1996; Gilbert, 1988; Otker, 1988). Insight is provided through recent developments in the literature to advance our understanding of sports sponsorship. In summary, any company entering into a sponsorship agreement should consider it as a resource, either alone or in combination with other resources, allowing it to develop into a unique capability that can in turn help the company gain a sustainable competitive advantage (Kaynak et al., 2008; Bodet & Bernache-Assollant, 2011).

Research Methodology and Objective

This study retrieves expert interview transcripts and relevant literature to understand customers' perceptions and recognition of sports brand sponsorship behavior and to understand whether sports brands can bring their customers closer together or influence consumers' brand loyalty, brand perceptions, brand impressions and purchase decisions through sponsorship. The findings obtained can be used as a reference for marketing designers of sports brands.

Conceptual Framework and Results

A conceptual framework for this paper can be summarized based on the references as follows :

H1: Customer communication has a positive impact on brand image perception

In marketing strategies, customer communication, as an important means of building customer relationships, not only improves the brand's service but also enhances the brand's image perception in the minds of customers (Rui, 2013).

Figure1. Conceptual framework of research (Rui, 2013; Boban, 2019; Shen & Gao, 2021)

H2: Brand image perception has a positive impact on customers' purchase decisions

By sponsoring high-value events or organizations, it creates brand awareness and recognition, improves building brand image, creates opportunities to participate in social responsibility activities, increases the financial value of the sponsor, and influences consumer purchase intentions and behavior (Boban, 2019).

H3: Sports sponsorship has a positive impact on customer communication

In the study, sports sponsorship as a form of customer communication can increase the perception of brand image, which leads to increased sales (Shen & Gao, 2021).

H4: Customer communication has a positive impact on customer purchase decisions

More specifically, for sponsors and their brands, sponsorship as one of the means of customer communication creates the opportunity to influence consumer perceptions and increase brand awareness, which results in driving sales (Rui, 2013; Boban, 2019; Shen & Gao, 2021).

H5: Sports sponsorship has a positive impact on brand image perception

The "standard rights package" for sponsors/partners includes a variety of standard exposure and usage, priority access to advertising, and marketing and promotional opportunities. While there are although sponsors choose to enter into sponsorship relationships for a number of purposes, the ultimate goal is to reach increased brand awareness, and as Owen, Sutton, and McCarthy point out (2008), corporate marketers see the value of associating with sports organizations, using sponsorship rights to teams, players, or events as a means to create awareness, develop brand image, and earn the loyalty of sports consumers (Owen, Sutton and McCarthy, 2008).

H6: Sports sponsorship has a positive impact on customer purchase decisions

Historically, the earliest cases of sports sponsorship can be considered as a form of entrepreneurial philanthropy or "patronage". In contrast, in contemporary times, sponsors aim to "tap" into a passion By working with their sponsorship targets, they develop strategies that leverage fans' loyalty and deep emotional connections to their teams and help drive them through customer communications, building brand image perceptions and ultimately driving sales (Shen & Gao, 2021).

Discussion

Nelson Mandela said at the inaugural Laureus World Sports Awards in 2000, "Sport has the power to change the world. It has the power to inspire. It has the ability to bring people together in a way that nothing else can. It speaks to young people in a language they understand. Sport can create hope where once there was only despair" (Biscaia et al., 2003). As the sports industry grows and is expected to reach a projected \$73.5 billion by 2019, we can expect to see a significant increase in sponsorship contracts involving corporations. We can expect a significant increase in sponsorship contracts involving corporations and sports athletes. Sponsorship contracts involving corporations and sports athletes will increase significantly (Boban, 2019). While many of us feel strongly about the positive impact of sports on social change, the key question at hand is. How can we more effectively leverage the billions of dollars of global sports sponsorship to drive more social good?

Attitudes toward sports sponsorship have a strong positive impact on the decision to purchase a sponsor's product. Therefore, the results obtained suggest that potential sports sponsors and advertisers, as well as investments in sustainability practices and initiatives, can have direct commercial benefits. In the long run, it can also indirectly differentiate and position the company in a saturated market. This relationship can certainly be used to further implement sustainable and socially responsible practices (Speed & Thompson, 2000). So far, the efforts of economic policy makers in different countries have mainly focused on creating legal frameworks and economic incentives for companies to integrate sustainability principles into their operations. At the same time, it is necessary to increase the awareness of society about the importance of these concepts in order to direct the consumption of individuals to purchase products produced according to sustainable production (Madrigal, 2001).

Actual sports fans in professional sports are often exposed to multiple sponsors from different industries (Chavanat, Martinet, & Ferrand, 2009), as sports teams are an important tool used by companies to strengthen their relationships with consumers (Bühler et al., 2007; Henseler et al., 2011). Since this study confirms that the relationship between sports organizations/clubs, fans and sponsors is very strong, leading to fans' purchasing decisions. Therefore sports sponsorship can be an effective way to promote the concept of corporate social responsibility and strengthen consumer confidence in socially responsible companies and their products. (Shaw & McDonald, 2006). For example, organizing different types of educational trainings in schools, organizing volunteer sports. Educational and promotional activities in retail stores, etc. (Roy & Cornwell, 2004).

Conclusion

The findings of the selected articles suggest that sponsorship is an investment in a cause or activity to support corporate goals (e.g., by improving corporate image) or marketing objectives (e.g., increasing brand awareness). This means that sponsorship can be either a strategic or a tactical tool. Sponsorship is intended to achieve a business objective and therefore is to be distinguished from activities of a purely charitable nature (donations). Sports sponsorship has a positive impact on sports fans' perceptions and attitudes towards sponsors and their products (Rui, 2013; Boban, 2019). Some other scholars (Shen & Gao, 2021) point out that sports sponsorship also has a significant positive impact on fans' purchasing decisions. Therefore, sports brands or sports products can promote customer communication and enhance brand image perceptions through sponsorship of sports organizations or events, which can have an impact on fans' attitudes and purchase decisions towards sports products and ultimately increase sales. At the same time, it also helps companies to realize their sustainable development concept through sports.

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